

Ionic Equilibria in Aqueous Solutions of Cadmium Perchlorate and Cadmium Nitrate

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Complete dissociation of cadmium perchlorate and cadmium nitrate in dilute aqueous solutions has been established from e.m.f. measurements of the cells ;

respectively, where Q.H. stands for quinhydrone. The concentrations of CdClO_4^+ and CdNO_3^+ ion in the experimental solutions are calculated from the knowledge of the dissociation constant of CdCl^+ and are found to be insignificant.

Recent work on cadmium perchlorate¹ and cadmium nitrate² has indicated that both are completely dissociated in dilute aqueous solutions. In their studies, Prasad and co-workers used salt bridges to eliminate liquid junction potential. The above conclusion has been tested with the following cells without liquid junction potential :

1. P. K. Jena and B. Prasad, *This Journal*, 1954, **31**, 480;
R. A. Metheson, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 439.
2. T. Moeller and P. W. Rhymer, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1942, **46**, 477;
R. A. Robinson, J. M. Wilson and H. S. Alying, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 1469;
D. Mangaraj, S. Aditya and B. Prasad, *This Journal*, 1953, **30**, 217.

where Q.H. stands for quinhydrone. In both the cells, there is negligible, if any, liquid junction potential.

EXPERIMENTAL

Analytical grade chemicals and double distilled water were used in the preparation of all solutions. Sodium perchlorate was prepared by neutralising a known volume of standard sodium carbonate solution with dilute perchloric acid. The electrode vessels, bridge, setting up of the cells and e.m.f. measurements were as described earlier³. The temperature of the air thermostat was constant within $25 \pm 0.05^\circ$. The e.m.f. values given in Table I and II are the mean values of duplicate readings taken in each case, which generally agreed within 0.1 mv. In a few cases the difference was 0.2 mv. The concentrations of cadmium chloride and hydrochloric acid were so chosen that the first stage, *i.e.*, $\text{CdCl}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CdCl}^+ + \text{Cl}^-$, of dissociation was complete. The symbol $[]_T$ denotes stoichiometric concentrations. All concentrations are expressed in gram moles/litre.

TABLE I

$[\text{HCl}]_T$	$[\text{CdCl}_2]_T$	$[\text{NaClO}_4]_T$	E.M.F.(E) volt	μ	$[\text{CdClO}_4^+]$
0.0020	0.0040	0.0080	0.14305	0.01932	0.00002
0.0025	0.0050	0.0100	0.15345	0.02380	0.00002
0.0030	0.0060	0.0120	0.16194	0.02816	0.00001
0.0035	0.0070	0.0140	0.16910	0.03250	0.00001
0.0040	0.0080	0.0160	0.17527	0.03672	0.00000
0.0045	0.0090	0.0180	0.18075	0.04084	0.00004
0.0050	0.0100	0.0200	0.18560	0.04500	0.00003

TABLE II

$[\text{HCl}]_T$	$[\text{CdCl}_2]_T$	$[\text{KNO}_3]_T$	E.M.F.(E) volt	μ	$[\text{CdNO}_3^+]$
0.0020	0.0040	0.0080	0.14310	0.01926	0.00008
0.0025	0.0050	0.0100	0.15347	0.02378	0.00002
0.0030	0.0060	0.0120	0.16202	0.02806	0.00009
0.0035	0.0070	0.0140	0.16916	0.03238	0.00009
0.0040	0.0080	0.0160	0.17530	0.03668	0.00003
0.0045	0.0090	0.0180	0.18075	0.04084	0.00004
0.0050	0.0100	0.0200	0.18566	0.04492	0.00012

DISCUSSION

The e.m.f. of the cell (A) as well as (B) is given by the equation

$$\frac{(E-E^\circ)F}{2.3026RT} = \log [H^+][Cl^-]f_Hf_{Cl}$$

which has been explained earlier (4).

The ionic strengths of the solutions in cell (A) and cell (B) are given by;

$$\mu = 2[Cd^{2+}] + \frac{1}{2}[CdCl^+] + \frac{1}{2}[CdClO_4^+] + \frac{1}{2}[H^+] + \frac{1}{2}[Cl^-] + \frac{1}{2}[Na^+] + \frac{1}{2}[ClO_4^-] \quad \dots (1)$$

and

$$\mu = 2[Cd^{2+}] + \frac{1}{2}[CdCl^+] + \frac{1}{2}[CdNO_3^+] + \frac{1}{2}[H^+] + \frac{1}{2}[Cl^-] + \frac{1}{2}[K^+] + \frac{1}{2}[NO_3^-] \quad \dots (2)$$

respectively. The concentrations of $CdClO_4^+$ and $CdNO_3^+$ in the respective experimental solution are computed using the method of successive approximations.

Let us take cell A. An arbitrary value is given to the ionic strength. The corresponding value of $[Cl^-]$ and $[CdCl^+]$ are calculated as described earlier⁴. The corresponding value of $[Cd^{2+}]$ is obtained from the relationship

$$K_{A(2)} = \frac{[Cd^{2+}][Cl^-]}{[CdCl^+]}$$

the value of $K_{A(2)}$ being known⁴ as a function of ionic strength. The corresponding value of $[CdClO_4^+]$ and $[ClO_4^-]$ are obtained from the relationships,

$$[Cd]_T = [CdClO_4^+] + [CdCl^+] + [Cd^{2+}]$$

and

$$[NaClO_4]_T = [CdClO_4^+] + [ClO_4^-]$$

respectively. Now $[H^+] = [HCl]_T$ and $[Na^+] = [NaClO_4]_T$. All concentration terms, corresponding to the arbitrary μ are known. A fresh value of ionic strength is obtained using equation (1). With this μ , a new set of values of the ionic concentrations and hence a new value of μ are obtained, following the above method. This process is repeated till the ionic concentrations and ionic strength become consistent and constant. The finally calculated values of ionic strength and $[CdClO_4^+]$ are given in Table I.

In case of cell (B) a similar procedure gives the value of $[CdNO_3^+]$ given in Table II. The calculated concentrations of $CdClO_4^+$ and $CdNO_3^+$ are so small that they can be taken to be zero within the experimental error. Hence it may be concluded that Cd^{2+} does not form ion pairs with either ClO_4^- or NO_3^- at least in dilute solutions.

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